

Vape Expo 2019 Survey

Vaping liquid flavour preferences, oral nicotine pouch and cannabis use among participants in the 2019 Oceania Vape Expo: Copy of the online survey

Marewa Glover¹, PhD, Carl V. Phillips², PhD, Kyro Selket¹, PhD, Yolande Jeffares¹, MSc

1. Centre of Research Excellence: Indigenous Sovereignty & Smoking, Auckland, New Zealand. 8 Toroa Street, Auckland, New Zealand, 0632. m.glover@coreiss.com [Corresponding author].
2. Epiphi Consulting, New Hampshire 03060, USA.

Funding statement

This study was funded with a grant from the Foundation for a Smoke-Free World, a US nonprofit 501(c)(3) private foundation with a mission to end smoking in this generation. The Foundation accepts charitable gifts from PMI Global Services Inc. (PMI); under the Foundation's Bylaws and Pledge Agreement with PMI, the Foundation is independent from PMI and the tobacco industry. The contents, selection, and presentation of facts, as well as any opinions expressed herein are the sole responsibility of the authors and under no circumstances shall be regarded as reflecting the positions of the Foundation for a Smoke-Free World, Inc. The Foundation had no involvement in the conception, design, analysis or writing of the study results, nor did they have any input into the decision to publish. The contents, selection, and presentation of facts, as well as any opinions expressed herein, are the sole responsibility of the authors.

*I understand the reason for the survey. I have read the Participant Information Sheet, and I have had a chance to ask questions about the survey.

Yes

No

*What is your age?

Under 18

18-24

24-35

36-50

51-65

65+

*Do you currently vape regularly? (Specifically, do you use nicotine e-cigarettes or vape non-nicotine e-liquid using devices designed for vaping nicotine, on most or all days?)

Yes

No

* Have you ever tried oral tobacco or nicotine pouches (a small pouch containing powdered tobacco “snus” or nicotine-soaked fibre that is placed under your top lip)?

Never heard of it

Have heard of it, but
haven't tried

Yes - I've tried

Do you currently use oral tobacco or nicotine pouches?

Yes

No

*What is your ethnicity? Please tick all that apply:

Maori

NZ European

Pacific Island

Chinese

Indian

Other

*Are you:

Male

Female

Other

*Where do you primarily reside?

In or near Auckland

Elsewhere in New Zealand

Outside New Zealand

*Do you vape zero nicotine?

- Exclusively Sometimes No
-

*Do you vape nicotine?

- Exclusively Sometimes No

*Which e-liquid flavour categories do you vape regularly (check all that apply)?

Tobacco

Menthol or mint

Fruit

Chocolate, sweets,
desserts

Coffee

Unflavoured

Other

*If only tobacco, menthol and mint flavours were legally allowed, and all other liquid flavours were **banned**, I would: (check all that apply)

Carry on as I am (I vape only tobacco, menthol or mint)

Just use what is legally allowed

Mix my own liquid

Buy other flavoured liquid from overseas or via the blackmarket

Probably go back to smoking

Try to stop vaping altogether

Other

Don't know

* Have you ever smoked more than 1 tobacco cigarette per day for at least one year? (= 365 cigarettes)

Yes

No

*Have you smoked more than 1000 tobacco cigarettes in your life? (This would be about 1 pack a week for 1 year, or 1 pack a day for 2 months, or 1 cigarette a day for 3 years.)

Yes

No

*How often do you currently smoke tobacco?

Never

Sometimes, but less
than once a week

At least once a week

Daily

*If you do not currently smoke, but did smoke in the past, how long ago did you stop smoking?

Less than one year ago

More than one year ago
but less than 3 years

More than 3 years ago

Never smoked

You may be eligible for a future study on the health effects of vaping.

If such a study was to come to Auckland, would you be interested in being a participant in it?

Yes

No

Maybe

Just a few more questions to go. Remember this survey is completely anonymous and there is no way your answers can be linked to you.

*How often do you smoke cannabis (marijuana)?

Never

Sometimes, but less
than once a week

At least once a week

Daily

*Have you ever vaped cannabis-based or cannabis-like liquids? Include e-liquids containing “THC” or “CBD” ? (If you think you have vaped one of these, but are not certain that is what it contained, please answer “yes”.)

Yes

No

*Where have you vaped THC or CBD?

In New Zealand

Overseas

*If cannabis is legalised in New Zealand, do you think you will vape CBD or THC?

No

Maybe

Almost certainly

Thank you for completing our survey.

If you would be willing to participate in future research with us, please register your interest on our website:
www.coreiss.com

Thank you for participating. Based on your answers, you are not eligible to continue this survey. Enjoy the Expo